

BPI Ri-4 is resistant to BPH biotype 1, appears to have field resistance to biotype 2, and is moderately resistant to stem borers. Current Masagana 99 crop protection recommendations do not include insecticide control for either "early" or "late" stem borers. BPH, a minor problem in the Philippines in 1978, was serious in 1977.

The average yields from 43 irrigated rice farms in 20 provinces are shown in the table.

Soil-incorporated granular carbofuran at as little as 0.5 kg a.i./ha returned high

Average yields from 43 irrigated farmers' fields in 20 provinces, Philippines, 1978 wet season.

Insecticide rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield increase (t/ha)	Value of increase at US\$0.15/kg	Cost of US\$ granular carbofuran	Increase in profit (US\$/ha)
0	4.0	—	—	—	—
0.5	4.7	0.7	105	15	90
0.75	5.0	1.0	150	22	128
1.00	5.1	1.1	165	30	135

^a Other Masagana 99 insect control recommendations: 5 kg ZnSO₄/ha, MTMC spray at 0.75 kg a.i./ha applied to all treatments 50 days after transplanting.

profits from the control of early season insect pests, primarily the whorl maggot and stem borers, on farms.

The Philippines may recommend soil

incorporation of granular carbofuran for the Masagana 99 national rice production program for the 1979 wet season (beginning in May). ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of insecticides against brown planthopper

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Of about 100 species of insect pests that attack rice in India, the brown planthopper (BPH) is the major one in many states. BPH epidemics have become frequent since about 1970. Chemical control measures are not satisfactory because the nymphs and adults remain at the base of the rice plant and the thick plant canopy forms an air cover, preventing the insecticidal spray from reaching them. To overcome this limitation studies were conducted to identify insecticides capable of killing the insect even if they are superficially applied on the crop foliage.

Aqueous solutions of 14 commercial insecticide preparations were applied as

0.05% sprays on the upper foliage of 1-month-old potted plants of TN1. The plants' basal 15-cm portions were covered with masks. The insecticides were sprayed with a fine atomizer until the runoff stage. The sprayed plants were kept in open air for 24 hours. Then the treated foliage was cut off and the plants were enclosed in cages. Ten healthy BPH adults were confined on each plant. Mortality was recorded at 12 and 24 hours after the insects' exposure to the treated plants. The experiment was replicated three times.

Chlorpyrifos had the highest systemic effect, followed by carbofuran, quinalphos, methamidophos, dicotophos, and phosphamidon (see table). The insecticides would be promising where the dense rice canopy prevents superficial insecticidal sprays from reaching the basal plant parts, where nymphs and adults remain. ■

Evaluation of systemic effect of some candidate insecticides applied as 0.05% foliar sprays against brown planthopper adults.^a 11-13 April 1977, Central Rice Research Institute, India.

Insecticide	Corrected mortality ^b (%)	
	12 hours	24 hours
Chlorpyrifos	100	100
Phosphamidon	33	63
Carbofuran	77	77
Carbaryl	40	40
Dicotophos	50	63
Monocrotophos	33	53
Quinalphos	47	67
Dimethoate	23	43
Methamidophos	50	67
SAN 197	0	30
Vamidothion	0	0
Dichlorvos	0	0
Control	0	0

^aMax temp = 34.4°C, min temp = 22.2°C, mean max temp = 33.7°C, mean min temp = 24.3°C, mean relative humidity = 74%.

^b Treated foliage portion cut off 24 hours after insects were exposed to treatment.

Emergence of rice leaf butterfly as a rice pest in Manipur, India

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Until 1973, the rice leaf butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene* Cramer was unknown to farmers of Manipur state. The first extensive infestation of the insect in the state was in 1973 kharif in Imphal, the central district, on a few new high-yielding and two local varieties (see table). The pest was noticed in the field in early August at the maximum tillering

stage of the main second crop and infestation continued until late November when the crop was almost mature. Horned caterpillars of the butterfly fed on the

tender foliage in late morning and early evening, and sometimes caused severe defoliation. Fields planted to second crops with ensured water supply were

Infestation of rice leaf butterfly on rice. Centra district, Imphal, Manipur, India

Variety	Location	Area infested ^a (ha)	Time	Plant parts infested
IR8	Changangei	4.05	Aug	Leaves
IR24	Kakching, Yurembam, Tabungkhok	81.00	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Ratna	Kakching	16.20	Jul-Aug	Leaves
Jaya	Changangei, Thoubal	4.05	Aug	Leaves
Moirangphou (local variety)	Kakching	40.50	Aug	Leaves, stem
Phourel (local variety)	Thoubal	6.07	Aug	Leaves, stem

^aConverted from acres.